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STATISTICAL LIFE PREDICTION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CF/PP TAPE UNDER CREEP TENSION LOAD

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Why Carbon with Polypropylene (PP) ?

- Light Weight : PP is lightest thermoplastic polymer
Density 0.9 g/cm^3
- Low moisture absorption
- Good processability and short processing cycle time
Compression molding,
Sheet insert injection molding,
Tape winding/Placement
- Solvent free : Environmental friendly
. . . But it was difficult to bond CF and PP.

Good Mechanical properties due to improvement of bonding PP/CF interface by custom sizing agent

Failure probability against failure time for a constant creep loading

Master curve of creep strength

$$\log \sigma_c = \log \sigma_0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_c^*(t, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right]$$

σ_0 scale parameter for the static strength at the reference temperature T_0 and failure time t_0

α shape parameter for the static strength at the reference temperature T_0 and failure time t_0

P_f failure probability

n_R viscoelastic parameter

E_c^* viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin

E_r relaxation modulus of matrix resin

Failure probability against failure time for a constant creep stress σ_{c0}

$$P_f = 1 - \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{\sigma_{c0}}{\sigma_0} \right]^\alpha \left[\frac{E_c^*(At, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right]^{n_R \alpha} \right\}$$

The creep failure probability of CFRP is represented as functions of applied creep stress, scale and shape parameters of static strength of CFRP and viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin.

Static and Creep Testing

Static Test Results and Parameter Determination

Weibull distributions of static tensile strength of CF/PP UD tape

Statistical static strength of CF/PP UD tape against viscoelastic compliance of PP

The static strength of CF/PP UD tape shows Weibull distribution in which the shape parameter keeps a constant for different temperatures except 150 °C and the scale parameter decreases with increasing temperature.

The static strength decreases linearly with increasing the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin. The viscoelastic parameter n_R can be determined by least square fitting. This parameter agrees well with that obtained from Rosen's failure model.

Now Creep Failure is Predictable !

The experimental results for the creep failure time agree well with predicted results.